

uppermost leaf sheath enclosing the infected internode remained healthy. Sections of tissues of the uppermost internode rotted and were covered with sooty spore masses. In late infection, grains developed poorly. The disease was more severe in dry fields than in wet

fields.

When microscopically examined, diseased samples collected from different rice-growing valley areas in the State consistently showed *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. The pathogen was isolated on rice straw extract agar medium and its

pathogenicity proved.

The sudden spread of the disease seems to have been influenced by cultivation of high-yielding, susceptible rice varieties and by a long dry spell during late growth stage. □

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Predators of rice insect pests in Chhattishgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Madhya Pradesh is situated between latitude 17° and 26°N and longitude 74° and 84°E. Rice is the predominant crop in Chhattishgarh, which has mixed red and yellow soil, 1,400-1,600 mm average rainfall, 85-95% average humidity, and

Predators of rice insect pests in Chhattishgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, India, 1984-86.

Predators	Prevalence
I Araneida	
Tetragnathidae	High
<i>Tetragnatha mandibulata</i>	
Lycosidae	
<i>Lycosa pseudoannulata</i>	Moderate
II Orthoptera	
Tettigoniidae	
<i>Conocephalus longipennis</i>	Moderate
III Odonota	
Coenagrionidae	
<i>Ischnura</i> sp.	Low
<i>Agriocnemis pygmaea</i>	High
IV Coleoptera	
Carabidae	Moderate
<i>Ophionea nigrofasciata</i>	
<i>Casnoidea indica</i>	Low
Coccinellidae	
<i>Coccinella arcuata</i>	Moderate
<i>Menochilus sexmaculata</i>	Low
<i>Scymnus postpinctus</i>	Low
Staphylinidae	
<i>Paederus fuscipes</i>	High
V Hemiptera	
Miridae	High
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	
Gerridae	Moderate
<i>Limnogonus</i> sp.	
<i>Microvelia</i> sp.	Moderate
Nabidae	
<i>Tropiconabis capsiformis</i>	Moderate

20-30 °C temperature during the Jun-Sep monsoon. Monsoon rice cultivation favors insect multiplication.

We counted natural enemies of monsoon rice pests in 1984-86 (see table). □

Effect of insecticides on eggs of *Brevennia rehi* (Lindinger)

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We tested the ovicidal action of 11 insecticides in the laboratory (see table).

For each treatment, 50 eggs were

placed in a petri dish lined with moist filter paper and sprayed with 1 ml spray solution, using an atomizer.

Eggs that hatched were counted every 15 min for 3 d. Data were converted into arc sin values and corrected for natural mortality using Abbott's formula.

BPMC 0.25 kg ai/ha delayed hatching most, and crawlers that hatched, died. □

Effect of insecticides on hatchability of *B. rehi* eggs.^a Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Hatchability (%)	Mortality (%)
Endosulfan	0.33	11 def	31 de
Phosphamidon	0.25	13 efg	22 f
Monocrotophos	0.20	10 def	36 de
Fenthion	0.50	11 cde	34 de
Chlorpyrifos	0.35	12 efg	22 f
Methyl demeton	0.125	10 c	39 d
Dimethoate	0.15	8 cd	51 c
Phosalone	0.35	12 efg	23 f
Biphenyl methyl carbamate	0.25	2 a	88 a
Deltamethrin	0.01	14 fg	14 g
Carbaryl	0.5	7 b	58 b
Control	-	14 g	-

^a Mean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are arc sin transformed values. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

Insect pests on main and ratoon rice

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Intan, a popular irrigated rice variety in the hilly region of Karnataka, was sown 5 Jul 1984 and 7 Jun 1985 in 8- × 1- ×

0.1-m nursery beds. Seedlings were transplanted 2 Aug 1984 in 64-m² plots and 13 Jul 1985 in 66-m² plots with 4 replications.

To supplement natural buildup of insect population, 15-20 20-m-long rows were maintained on each side of the experimental field. No insecticides were

Insect pests on main crop and ratoon crop of Intan at Mudigere, India. OHLH = orange-headed leafhopper, WM = whorl maggot, CW = caseworm, LR = leafroller, T = thrips, GM = gall midge, SB = stem borer, GLH = green leafhopper, BPH = brown planthopper.

used. The crop was harvested on 31 Dec 1984 and 25 Nov 1985 leaving 8-cm stubble. The ratoon crop was fertilized with 45 kg urea 30 d after main crop harvest.

Insects were sampled on main crop and ratoon crop using a sweep net. Ten criss-cross sweeps were made at the top of the canopy on each plot and selected species counted. Plants also were examined for noticeable damage. In 1985, natural enemies were also sampled following the same sampling methods.

The ratoon crop recorded significantly higher numbers of orange-headed leafhopper *Thaia subrufa* (Motsch.) and green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) than the main crop in both 1984 and 1985 (see figure). Brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) had significantly higher numbers on the ratoon crop in 1985.

Whorl maggot *Hydrellia griseola* (Fallen), caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guenée), leafroller *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée), gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason), and thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis*

(Bagn.) did not increase. Stem borers *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walk.) and *S. innotata* (Walk.) damaged both the main and ratoon crops.

Both main and ratoon crops harbored natural enemies that can play a crucial role in suppressing insect pests.

Six spiders, 2 odonatan, 2 wasps, 1 neuropteran, 16 *Cyrtorhinus* sp., and 12 *Microvelia* sp. bugs were recorded per 10 clumps on the main crop. On the ratoon crop, one spider, two odonatan, one neuropteran, six *Cyrtorhinus*, and two *Microvelia* spp. were recorded. □

Electronically recorded waveforms associated with brown planthopper (BPH) feeding activity

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We analyzed the feeding activity of BPH by an electronic measurement system constructed with a power supply unit, variable oscillator, logarithmic amplifier, and stripchart recorder. BPH behavioral components associated with feeding activity were recorded as different voltage fluctuation patterns.

A brachypterous female was tethered with a 10- μ m-diameter gold wire leading to the input of the electric current detection amplifier using electric conductive paint Dotite D-550 and allowed to feed on a potted rice plant electrified by applying a 500 Hz, 5 V alternative current from the oscillator. The plant and BPH were confined in a copper net cage during measurement to shut off electric noise.

BPH is a phloem feeder, with stylet sheath feeding. Its feeding process consisted of probing and sucking phases that elicited distinct waveforms. When the BPH started to penetrate the plant epidermis, an abrupt upsurge of electric current appeared. This is possibly due to excretion of a bulk of sheath material